

Spatial arithmetic explains mass, energy, and particles – Law of conservation of spatial value

We have the full energy formula:

$$E = \gamma m_0 c^2$$

With

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

We have: $E^2 = (m_0)^2 c^4 / (1 - v^2/c^2)$

$$\Leftrightarrow E^2 = (m_0)^2 c^4 / (1 - q^2/(t^2 c^2))$$

$$\Leftrightarrow E^2 = (m_0)^2 c^4 / (1 - SV/t^2) \text{ (SV = } q^2/c^2 \text{: is the spatial value for space transformation)}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow E^2 = (m_0)^2 c^4 / ((t^2 - SV)/t^2)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow E^2 = (m_0)^2 c^4 / (t'^2/t^2)$$

$$E^2 = (m_0)^2 c^4 / (t'^2/t^2) \text{ hoặc } E^2 (1 - SV/t^2) = (m_0)^2 c^4$$

E is energy, the kinetic energy that creates spatial value, equivalent to 1 S or a spatial fraction $c^2 \text{ km}^2$. Thus, we can represent (map)

$E = tc^2$. Here, it doesn't mean E increases over time, but rather represents the creation of spatial value.

Consider 1 unit of energy c^2 (Note that c^2 here is the name of the energy unit I propose, not $c \times c$).

Substituting, we get: $m_0 = t'$

Thus, mass is essentially the spatial value of the energy unit c^2 that has not yet been transformed into space.

And: $SV \cdot c^2 = p^2$. This means that the square of momentum is the portion of spatial value that is transformed into space.

Thus, the energy formula can be rewritten as follows:

$$E^2 = SV \cdot c^4 + (m_0)^2 c^4$$

$$\text{Or } t^2 c^4 = SV \cdot c^4 + t'^2 c^4 \text{ or } t^2 = SV + t'^2$$

This is also the Law of Conservation of Spatial Value.

Thus, a unit of energy c^2 , if operating freely (completely transformed into space), has no mass, unlike photons. Therefore, photons are essentially bundles of energy units, each unit of energy completely transformed into space, thus achieving velocity c and having no rest mass or time. Having mass implies having time, which is the value of the untransformed space.

If the energy unit does not completely transform into space, it will have mass and therefore cannot reach the speed of light c , as is the case with electrons or even neutrinos.

Among the various types of photons, the Ultra-Low Wave (ELF) photon has the lowest energy currently known. We can consider this to be 1 unit of energy c^2 . Visible light photons have an energy level about 100 trillion times higher (100 trillion units of energy c^2).

More or less energy does not necessarily mean mass. Whether or not a particle has mass depends on how the energy bundles within the particle are distributed to create space. However, from the Law of Conservation of Spatial Value, we can calculate the conversion between different types of particles (whether or not mass is formed).

This is only a personal viewpoint that I would like to share from my own reflections. Thank you for reading these lines.